

Research

Studies on β - Glucuronidase enzyme inhibition and insecticidal activity from Echinops Echinatus

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Abstract: β -glucuronidase is a common enzyme which cleaves in β linkage and converts aglycone to a glucuronic acid. Studies have been made on this enzyme and a lot of work has been reported about specific inhibition of β -glucuronidase enzyme and insecticidal activity while to the best of our knowledge current work was conducted to check the β - Glucuronidase enzyme inhibition and insecticidal activity of a plant *Echinops Echinatus* for the first time. Methanol and DCM extracts of *Echinops Echinatus* showed weak insecticidal activity while moderate results of β -Glucuronidase enzyme Inhibition were observed.

Keywords: β -glucuronidase_ *Echinops Echinatus*_ enzyme_ insecticidal activity

Introduction

Echinops echinatus Roxb (Family Asteraceae), is a pubescent annual herb of 1–3 feet in height, distributed throughout Pakistan and India. Different parts especially roots of this plant are being sold in different Pakistani and Indian markets under the trade name of brahmadandi and are used in curing of different disorders related to the reproductive system i.e abortifacients, to fasten delivery process in females, as a diuretic in urinary discharges and in syphilis. Antifertility effects of *E. echinatus* roots and its various extracts showed antiestrogenic activities in female rats during experimental studies. We investigated antifungal, inhibitory activity against β -Glucuronidase enzyme and insecticidal activity from the methanolic constituents of *Echinops echinatus* resulted in isolation of flavones, echinacin and echinaticin with apigenin and another glucoside apignin 7-o-glucoside. Methyl and DCM extracts derivatives were tested for the first time against insects like *Tribolium castaneum*, *Callosbruchus analis* and *Rhyzopertha dominica*

by contact toxicity method. The dichloromethane extract showed low activity against *Callosbruchus analis* while methanolic extract was non significant against all the insects. The sample extracts of both the components i.e methanol extract and dichloromethane extract exhibited moderate inhibitory activity against β - Glucuronidase enzyme.

Echinops echinatus (Indian globe thistle)

Materials and methods

Whole plant *Echinops echinatus* was collected from Cholistan desert in second week of May, Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan, Whole plant was washed and shade dried in a room. A sample for specimen was preserved in school of Pharmacy, further following materials and methods were performed.

Extraction of *Echinops echinatus*

Whole plant of *Echinops echinatus* which was collected from Cholistan desert of Pakistan was dried in shade for 25 days. Whole Plant of *Echinops echinatus* was then pulverized by machine and was weighed (200 gram). The powdered plant material *Echinops echinatus* was further subjected for simple maceration with methanol (MeOH) and another portion with dichloromethane (DCM) and then it was extracted. Powdered whole plant of *Echinops echinatus* was soaked in 1 liter of dichloromethane (DCM) in a closed glass vessel (72hrs). The vessel containing this mixture, with DCM solvent was used to be shaken occasionally so that maximum

possible extraction should be achieved, in a similar way the extraction of powdered *Echinops echinatus* marc was further done with the solvent MeOH. Further solvents were removed through rotary evaporator under reduced pressure. Two wide mouth jars were taken and both the extracts were labeled with specific codes and stored in jars with the lids open for one week, after one week the extracts were dried fully and they were weighed again.

A view of Cholistan desert, Bahawalpur, Punjab Pakistan

Phytochemical Analysis of *Echinops echinatus*

Different chemical tests were performed for phytochemical constituents for evaluation and evaluation of crude plant material of *Echinops echinatus*. A specific chemical test which is already reported in literature is done for a single type or a single compound; and some general chemical tests are performed for a specific group of phytochemical constituents. Production of colors is also involved in some sorts of tests.

Chemical Tests for Identification of Constituents

Borntrager's test was employed on *Echinops echinatus* extracts to confirm the presence of anthraquinones, Keller kelliani test was also performed to check the presence or the absence of cardiac glycosides in *Echinops echinatus*, Saponins in *Echinops echinatus* were also detected by specific procedure in the plant of *Echinops echinatus*. Tannins presence in the fully ripened whole plant of *Echinops echinatus* were checked using the procedures such as FeCl₃ test and Gelatin test.

Mobile phases for TLC analysis of DCM and methanol extracts for fully ripened *Echinops echinatus*.

Mobile Phases applied for analysis of Dichloromethane(DCM) crude extracts	Ratios
<i>n</i> -hexane : Ethyl Acetate	80:20
	60:40
	50:50
Chloroform : Methanol: Water	80:20:2
Solvent Systems used for analysis of Methanol crude extract	Ratios
Ethyl acetate: Methanol : Water	100:10:5
	100:14:7
	100:20:10

Figure TLC chromatogram of Methanol extract of whole plant of *Echinops echinatus*

Figure: TLC chromatogram of DCM extract of whole plant of *Echinops echinatus*

Comparative analysis of compound of four fractions A= 1-7, B= 8-15 ,C= 16-24 ,D= 25-30

Fractionation results of Methanol extract of whole plant of *Echinops echinatus*.

Different Pooled fractions	Color of each fraction	Weight of each fraction (mg)
EEWM-A (1-7)	Dark green	339
EEWM-B (8-15)	Light-green	372
EEWM-C (16-24)	Light yellow	378
EEWM-D (25-30)	Yellow	348
EEWM-E (Washing fraction)	Light yellow	359

Methanol extract fractionation sketch of *Echinops echinatus*

7-hydroxyisoflavone (15 mg), yellowish granules, Rf 0.52, mp 215°C ; kaempferol-40-methylether(21 mg), yellow shining granules, Rf 0.45,mp 223–225°C;kaempferol-7-methylether (28 mg), yellow granules, Rf 0.38, mp 218-220°C, kaempferol (31 mg), yellow granules, Rf 0.32, 273–275°C; kaempferol-3-O-a-L-rhamnoside (28 mg), yellow shining granules, Rf 0.20,mp 177–179°C; myrecetin-3-O-a-L-rhamnoside(24 mg), yellow granules, Rf 0.10,mp 211–213°C and a new flavone glycoside, echinoside were also isolated from above solvent fractions.

Structural formula of flavone and flavone glycoside

Biological Activities of *Echinops echinatus* extracts:

Methanol and DCM extracts of whole plant, fully ripened *Echinops echinatus* were also biologically tested for anti cancer (Hela cell line, PC₃ cell line, 3T3 cell line), insecticidal, brine-shrimp lethality assay, Enzyme inhibition, alpha-glucuronidase, β glucuronidase enzyme inhibition bioassays. We performed different assays for this biological screening of *Echinops echinatus* samples extracts.

Insecticidal Activity of *Echinops echinatus*

To store and develop an excellent quality grains, it's necessary to free the grains from insect's contamination and insect's infestation (Collins, P. J. 1998). Majority of the insects which are causative agents for this insect's contamination and insect's infestation are Lepidoptera (8-9%) and Coleoptera (60%).

Mostly following bioassays or techniques are used to confirm insecticidal activities:

1. Toxicity method on different toxic surfaces (Choudhary *et al.*, 2001)
2. Insecticidal impregnated dust method on grains
3. Impregnated filter paper method of grains (Tabassum R *et al.*, 1997)
4. Directly spraying of chemicals on grains (Champ B. R, 1981).

Some common stored grain pests detail is given in following table

Name of pests	Rearing media	Rearing temperature in (°C)	Life Cycle (Days)	Relative humidity (%)
<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>	Flour of wheat	30	22-25	50-70
<i>Sitophilus oryzae</i>	Rice and flour	25	26-28	50-70
<i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i>	Gram and wheat seeds	30	30	50-70
<i>Trogoderma granarium</i>	wheat	30	30	50-70
<i>Callosobruchus analis</i>	Seeds of mung	25-35	25-30	50-70

Filter paper impregnated test:

Requirements:

Test organisms/insects such as *Callosobruchus analis*, *Rhyzopertha dominica*, *Trogoderma granarium*, *Tribolium castaneum* and *Sitophilus oryzae*. Some quantity of volatile organic solvent i.e acetone, methanol and ethanol, Permethrin was used as a standard insecticidal drug, 1000µl of some micropipette, some petri dishes (diameter 9 cm), a specific chamber for growth, some filter papers, a brush, glass vials and test sample.

Preparation for test sample:

3 ml volatile solvent and 200 mg test sample is taken as crude sample

3 ml volatile solvent and 20 mg test sample

Rearing Technique:

Sterile breeding media containing some plastic bottles were selected. A lab restricted circumstances or atmosphere is created like specific humidity and temperature and above pests stored in grains were reared in this lab restricted atmosphere. For this experiments such insects were taken which have uniform age and size.

Procedure:

On Day-1:

A specific size (9 cm or 90 mm), petri plate is cut, a filter paper was also cut in accord to petri plate size 9 cm or cut in 90 mm size, filter paper was put in this plate. After this by using micropipette all the sample extract is loaded over it. To get complete evaporation and good results, these plates were placed in open atmosphere for 24 hours.

On 2nd Day:

When all the solvent in petri plates is evaporated completely after 24 hrs, then with the help of clean brush 10 insects (both control and test specie) from each groups were put on each of the ten prepared petri plates. Those Insects were selected which had good physical shapes, active and had same age and same size. These plates were incubated at 27 °C for 24 hours in a growth chamber by using relative humidity 50%.

On 3rd Day:

After 24 hours those insects were counted which were survived after performing this procedure. Following formula was used to calculate the percentage of mortality and percentage of inhibition.

$$\text{Percentage Mortality} = 100 - \frac{\text{No. of insects alive in tests}}{\text{No. of insects alive in control}} \times 100$$

Control study:

Negative and positive controls are screened by test compounds. A standard insecticidal drug, permethrin was used to test those insects which were present in positive control, while in negative control tests volatile solvent is present.

Results of Insecticidal activity

In current research work to confirm insecticidal activity of methanol (MeOH) extract and dichloromethane (DCM) of *Echinops echinatus* was evaluated against *Tribolium castaneum*, *Callosbruchus analis* and *Rhyzopertha dominica* by contact toxicity method. Permethrin was a standard drug in this test while concentration of sample was 1019.10 µg/cm² and conc of standard drug permethrin was 239.5 µg/cm². We noticed that dichloromethane extract exhibited

low activity against insects *Callosbruchus analis* while the methanol extract was non significant against any insect. Detailed results are given below.

The Insecticidal activity results of whole plant of *Echinops echinatus* in Dichloromethane (EEWPD) sample extract by contact toxicity method.

Name of Insects	%Mortality		Sample results
	+ve Control	-ve Control	
<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>	100	0	0 %
<i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i>	100	0	0%
<i>Callosbruchus analis</i>	100	0	20%

Conc. Of sample 1019.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ Std. Drug Permethrin Conc. Of Std.Drug 239.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$

The Insecticidal activity results of whole plant of *Echinops echinatus* in Methanol (EEWPM) sample extract by contact toxicity method.

Name of Insects	%Mortality		Sample results
	+ve Control	-ve Control	
<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>	100	0	0 %
<i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i>	100	0	0%
<i>Callosbruchus analis</i>	100	0	0%

Conc. Of sample 1019.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ Std. Drug Permethrin Conc. Of Std.Drug 239.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$

Enzyme inhibition studies:

β – Glucuronidase enzyme inhibition activity

β -Glucuronidase enzyme is exoglycosidase enzyme which is involved in catalyzation of cleavage of glucuronosyl-O-bonds. B-Glucuronidase enzyme belongs from hydrolyses class of enzymes, distributed intracellularly in lysosomal and microsomal fractions of various cells. Different cells of blood, various organs, different body fluids, liver, spleen, bile, kidney, urine, muscles, lungs, serum and gastric juice also contain B-Glucuronidase enzyme. β -Glucuronidase enzyme inhibition activity was performed in 0.1 M acetate at buffer pH 7 against cancerous cells, various hepatic diseases, inflammatory joint disorders and even against AIDS. Different concentrations of various compounds which were going to be checked i.e buffers and different enzyme were also incubated for 30 minutes at 37 °C. A Compound *P*-nitrophenyl- β -D-glucuronide with concentration 0.4 mM was also added into it, then with help of a specific

molecular device, the 96-well plates at 405 nm were read on Spectral Max plus 384 (Khan KM *et al.*, 2002).

β-Glucuronidase Enzyme inhibition results:

D-Sacchamic acid 1,4-lactone was used as a standard inhibitor, β-Glucuronidase a digestive enzyme, the inhibitory effects of EEWPD and EEWPM sample extracts were assessed. D-Sacchamic acid which was standard inhibitor was used in standard conc 0.4mM, 1,4-lactone was used for this purpose. The sample extracts of both the components showed inhibitory activity against β- Glucuronidase enzyme. The results of both the extracts are given as follows.

β-Glucuronidase Enzyme Inhibition results of *Echinops echinatus*

Sample	Concentration (mM)	% Inhibition	IC ₅₀ ±SEM[μM]
EEWD	0.4	83.5	119.1±12.5
EEWM	0.4	61.6	293.1±7.50
D-Sacchamic acid 1,4-lactone (Standard)	0.4	89.4	45.75±2.16

Conclusion

In conclusion *Echinops echinatus* methanol and DCM extract showed weak insecticidal activity while moderate results of β-Glucuronidase enzyme inhibition were observed. Different researchers have reported different types of activities of plant *Echinops echinatus* such as anti inflammatory, anti fungal and some activities on male reproductive organ while insecticidal activity and β-Glucuronidase Enzyme inhibition activity is going to be reported for the first time.

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Dedication

All my dedications go to my late father. May his soul rest in peace..!

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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